

Study Registration is the process of adding a new study to the RADx Data Hub. Before users add a new study, an NIH Officer must supply RADx Data Hub Data Curators with the completed Material Transfer Agreement (MTA). The Data Curators will upload the MTA into the system. After that, users will receive an automated email notification to add additional study metadata and will be able to find their study in their Study Registration Dashboard. After receiving the email users should:

1. Click “Study Registration” under “Data Submitter” in the navigation bar (Figure 1). The system will navigate you to the Study Registration Dashboard (Figure 2).

Figure 1: The Study Registration option in the Upper Navigation Bar

2. Locate the newly added study in the table and click the “Edit” link. The entry status should read “Pending DCC Input” (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Study Registration Dashboard

Please view a form by clicking an edit icon below.

PHS	Study Name	Status	Created Date	Edit
phs007001	For Testing - RADx/ Study Registration Information	Pending DCC Input	4/17/2024	
phs002650	Building Resiliency and Vital Equity (BRAVE)	In Review	11/15/2021	
phs002873	The Cherokee Nation Community-Driven Program for Testing and Contract Tracing (Cherokee PROTECT)	In Review	4/20/2022	
phs003021	Community Organizations for Natives: COVID-19 Epidemiology, Research, Testing, and Services (CONCERTS)	In Review	8/12/2022	
phs003366	You & Me: Test and Treat	In Review	7/27/2023	
phs003368	SCALE UP Utah II: Community-Academic Partnership to Address COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination Among Utah Community Health Centers	In Review	7/28/2023	

- Fill in blank “(C)DCC Input” metadata fields (Figure 3). Users may review the MTA form by clicking “Download Study PDF” in the top-right.

Figure 3: Study Registration Form (Submitter View)

The screenshot shows the 'Study Registration Form (Submitter View)'. At the top, there are two main sections: 'RADx Data Program' and '* Study Name'. The 'RADx Data Program' section has a dropdown menu with 'RADx-rad' selected and a 'PHS (dbGaP) ID' field with 'phs002685' entered. The '* Study Name' field contains 'DNA Sur SAS-CoV-2 Rapid Test'. Below these is a navigation bar with a '< Return to Dashboard' button, a message 'Please review and edit these fields if necessary.', and a 'Download Study PDF' button highlighted with a red box. The main section is titled '(C)DCC Input' and contains several fields: '* FOA Number' (empty), '* Study Start Date' (MM/DD/YYYY), '* Study End Date' (MM/DD/YYYY), '* Study Topics' (dropdown menu), 'Other Topics, Specify' (text input), '* Data Collection Methods' (dropdown menu), 'Other Data Collection Methods' (text input), '* Keywords' (text input), 'Clinical Trials.gov URL' (text input), 'Study Website URL' (text input), and 'Primary Publication URL' (text input). Each text input field has a '+ Add' button next to it.

- Click “Submit” button at the bottom of the form to send it to the RADx Data Hub Data Curators for review. The Data Curators will reach out with any questions.

Note: To edit study metadata fields that were in the original MTA form, contact the Data Curators using the “Contact Us” feature. Users cannot edit data using the system’s user interface.